

A Brief Overview of Some Federal Systems and Restructuring in Nepal

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Abstract:

Modern politics endorses various governing systems, with the unitary and federal systems being the primary forms. These systems can change in response to the immediate needs of a country, influenced by the will of the people and the interests of leadership. Some unitary states have transitioned to federal systems, while some federal systems have disintegrated, depending on the circumstances and necessities of the state. In the context of conflict management, Nepal has transitioned from a unitary system to federalism through state restructuring. The primary reason for this shift was the internal

conflict within the state. This article focuses on the federalism adopted by Nepal, examining the experiences of major federal countries worldwide and discussing Nepal's approach to federalism. The study attempts to address and find solutions to several pertinent questions regarding this transition.

Keywords: *constitution, federalism, governance, system, unitary.*

Introduction

Background

In modern politics, various types of governance systems exist, with federalism being one such form. A unitary system centralizes state power, devolving authority from the top down based on law. In contrast, federalism divides state power constitutionally, allowing lower organs to

regulate and govern. Thus, federalism is a governance system that constitutionally distributes statutory power.

The division of power in governmental systems has a long history. Almond, Powell, Strom, and Dalton (2004) noted that the origins of this concept in modern politics can be traced back to Montesquieu and John Locke. By the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, two main practices

emerged in political theory: the United Kingdom's parliamentary system and the United States' presidential system (p. 104). Some federal states have been established to address governance issues, enhance political participation, and meet crucial national needs.

The United States was the first country to adopt modern federalism, leading the way with a presidential system. However, not all federal countries follow this model. As Ray (1999) observed, "Federalism has no specific principle and no universally accepted nature" (p. 150). Consequently, countries adopt federalism in their own ways based on their unique needs and circumstances. Currently, 28 countries worldwide have adopted federalism, each with its own reasons and obligations.

For this study, five countries have been selected: the United States, Ethiopia, Germany, India, and Switzerland, alongside Nepal. These countries were chosen based on factors such as ethnicity, geography, population, and political structure. The formation of Nepal's federalism is a central topic of this research. This article discusses the basis for establishing federalism in Nepal and compares it to the foundations of federalism in the selected countries.

Statement of the Problem

The will of the people and the current situation of a country play pivotal roles in determining its governance system. Throughout history, the type of governance adopted by a nation often reflects the collective aspirations of its people and the unique circumstances it faces. This dynamic interplay between popular will and situational needs is particularly evident in the formation and evolution of federal systems. Federalism, characterized by the constitutional division of power among various levels of government, emerges as a response to specific socio-political conditions and demands. This article delves into the critical factors influencing the adoption of federalism, with a particular focus on addressing two fundamental research questions:

- Were obligatory or vigilant conditions the primary drivers for the establishment of federalism in various countries?
- Was it necessary for Nepal to implement federalism instead of continuing with a unitary system?

Objectives

Federalism often arises as a pragmatic response to obligatory and vigilant conditions, such as ethnic diversity, geographical expanse, socio-economic disparities, and political fragmentation. In ethnically diverse nations, federalism can ensure representation and autonomy for various groups, mitigating conflicts and fostering unity. For instance, Ethiopia's federal system, established in the 1990s, aimed to accommodate its many ethnic groups and prevent ethnic strife. Similarly, post-World War II Germany adopted federalism to balance power among its distinct regions, ensuring no single region could dominate.

Federalism also emerges from vigilant conditions where central government control is seen as inadequate or oppressive. This often stems from regional demands for greater autonomy and self-governance. India's federal structure evolved to address the diverse needs of its vast population, balancing regional autonomy with national integrity. This arrangement was crucial for managing India's profound linguistic, cultural, and religious diversity. Nepal's shift from a unitary to a federal system was driven by internal conflicts and the demand for inclusivity and representation. The decade-long Maoist insurgency exposed deep issues of inequality and marginalization, highlighting the unitary system's limitations. The 2006 Comprehensive Peace Agreement set the stage for a more inclusive political framework. Federalism in Nepal aimed to decentralize power, empowering local governments to address specific needs, promote development, and reduce regional disparities. This transition reflected the people's will, emerging from grassroots movements and public consultations that sought to accommodate Nepal's ethnic, cultural, and geographical diversity. Federalism thus became a necessary evolution for Nepal, addressing

historical injustices and aligning with the aspirations for a more inclusive and representative governance system. This study focuses on the following two objectives:

- To investigate whether obligatory or vigilant conditions were the primary drivers for the establishment of federalism in various countries.
- To determine if it was necessary for Nepal to implement federalism instead of continuing with a unitary system.

Methodology

The primary objective of this study is to determine whether the federal system was inevitable and necessary for Nepal, as opposed to maintaining a unitary system. Additionally, it seeks to understand the reasons behind the implementation of federalism in five specific countries: the United States, Ethiopia, Germany, India, and Switzerland. In this context, the study discusses and analyzes the justifications for the establishment of federalism in Nepal, comparing them with the factors that led to federal structures in these countries. The research identifies significant characteristics that played crucial roles in the restructuring processes of these nations. It examines obligatory and vigilant conditions that necessitated the formation of federal states. The study aims to uncover the foundations of federalism in these countries and apply these insights to the case of Nepal. Descriptive and analytical approaches are employed, relying solely on secondary data. The descriptive method involves analyzing various theoretical reviews of federal systems. The study also identifies and examines dependent variables and other methodological components under appropriate conditions. Through this comprehensive analysis, the study attempts to place Nepal's federalism within a broader international context, highlighting the factors that made federalism a necessary choice for the country.

Discussion

Today, political science scholars continue to grapple with the concepts of federalism and sovereignty, often presenting sophisticated interpretations and insights. Despite extensive study, many questions about these topics remain unresolved. Jean Bodin's classical theory of sovereignty, for instance, has been revisited and reinterpreted in the context of contemporary federalism. As Merkl (1975) states, "Federalism is seen as a measure between the confederation and the unitary system" (p. 331). This ongoing discourse provides a rich field for discussion and research, particularly in examining the conditions under which various countries have adopted federalism.

This article aims to explore the circumstances leading to the adoption of federalism in nations such as the United States, Ethiopia, Germany, India, Switzerland, and Nepal. Unlike other political systems, federalism does not adhere to a single, compulsory principle. However, it does share some fundamental characteristics, such as a written constitution, a minimum of a two-tier government structure, and constitutional guarantees of rights and responsibilities among different levels of government.

Historically, some countries have transitioned from a unitary to a federal system, while others have moved in the opposite direction, dissolving their federal structures. As Topperwien (2009) notes, "Federalism is certainly no miracle cure and may not be appropriate for all countries and all situations. There are successful examples of federal states, but also a long list of failed federations" (p. 80). The success of federalism often depends on the state's values, the consent of its people, and the prevailing political desires. Each state's unique legal and political context can make federalism suitable, highlighting the need for case-by-case analysis.

The situation in Nepal provides a pertinent case study. Before the implementation of its federal system, there was little public discussion or debate about advanced decentralization. The topic was largely kept under wraps, as was the debate over whether to adopt federalism or a unitary system with enhanced decentralization.

These issues warrant separate, in-depth studies to understand the lack of transparency and public engagement during this critical period.

Changes in governance systems typically reflect the needs of the country and the will of its people. Studying global federalism reveals that its adoption often stems from pressing, unavoidable issues. In Nepal, the shift to federalism is closely tied to the Maoist movement and the subsequent drafting of a new constitution. This new constitution, aimed at managing the Maoist insurgency, replaced Nepal's long-standing unitary system. Although the Interim Constitution of 2007 sought to integrate the Maoists into the political mainstream, it ultimately paved the way for federalism.

This article attempts to explore why federalism was deemed necessary in Nepal, comparing it with other countries where federalism became inevitable. It examines the binding factors that drove these countries to adopt federalism and discusses similar issues in the context of Nepal. Through this comparative analysis, the study seeks to uncover the underlying reasons that made federalism a necessary governance model for Nepal and to highlight the broader implications of adopting such a system. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of the conditions that make federalism a viable and sometimes essential choice for diverse political landscapes

The United States of America

The origins of federalism can be traced back to the drafting of the United States Constitution, marking a pivotal moment in the history of modern governance. With the establishment of the Constitution in Philadelphia in 1787, the United States embarked on a revolutionary path, introducing three groundbreaking innovations: a new nation, modern federalism, and a presidential system. As Watts (2008) notes, "The United States had adopted federalism as an organized principle for the formation of the government in 1787, following the Convention of 1777" (p. 29). These constitutional innovations were uniquely American, representing the culmination of the country's

aspirations for self-governance and political autonomy.

The journey towards modern federalism began with the American Continental Congress of 1774 in Philadelphia, which marked the onset of a new era for America. Grievances over British taxation ignited discontent among Americans, leading to a series of gatherings and discussions. On June 7, 1776, amidst growing unrest, Richard Lee of Virginia called for a proclamation of independence, laying the groundwork for the American Confederation. Over the ensuing decade, the Confederation faced numerous challenges, prompting the need for a more robust system of governance.

The transformation from the Confederation to the modern federation was formalized in 1789, following the Philadelphia Convention of 1787. As Watts (2008) observes, "Following the American Revolution, the newly independent states established a confederation in 1781. Its deficiencies, however, led to its transformation in 1789, following the Philadelphia convention of 1787, into the first modern federation" (p. 3). This transition underscored the necessity of forging a sovereign political identity in the aftermath of the Revolution.

The process of drafting the Constitution was not without challenges. The initial acceptance of the Confederation law did not exert control over all participating states and was plagued by instability. According to Bhagawan & Bhushan (1988), in 1787, Alexander Hamilton proposed a new constitution during the Congress convened in Annapolis. Subsequently, a meeting of 12 states in Philadelphia agreed to draft a constitution, culminating in 12 weeks of intensive discussions and the eventual signing of the draft by all 13 states (p. 6). The history of the United States reveals a complex interplay between independence and unity among the states. Despite their individual sovereignty, the states were compelled to unite in the face of external pressures, giving rise to a unique form of federalism characterized by cooperation and shared governance. This innovative model paved the way for the development of modern federal systems worldwide, serving as a

testament to the enduring legacy of America's revolutionary spirit.

Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia

The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia stands as a multi-ethnic and religious federal parliamentary state. Established in 1995 following the democratic revolution, Ethiopia's federal system was crafted to accommodate its vast ethnic and religious diversity. The country's population, marked by its size and diversity, necessitated the adoption of a federal structure, with administrative units organized along ethnic lines.

Ethiopia's federation grants significant powers to its regional states to address the needs of its diverse population. Despite Amharic being the official language, each region has the autonomy to designate its own language, reflecting the country's rich linguistic tapestry comprising over 80 languages and 200 dialects. Notably, Ethiopia's constitution uniquely outlines the right of subnational units to secede from the federation and establishes a process for ethnic groups within existing states to form new regions (Watts, 2008, p. 48).

Indeed, Ethiopia's federalism is deeply rooted in its ethnic diversity, with nine predominantly ethnic regions and two chartered cities. However, the country faces formidable challenges, including widespread poverty and an economy heavily reliant on rainfall patterns. Ethnic diversity poses a significant internal challenge, with historical ethnic conflicts contributing to the country's instability. Consequently, the adoption of federalism in 1994 was deemed necessary to address these challenges and safeguard national unity (Ethiopia government portal, 2020-09-16).

The establishment of a democratic federal state structure in Ethiopia was a deliberate effort to accommodate settlement patterns, linguistic identities, and the consent of its diverse population. The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia comprises two legislative bodies: the Council of the People's Representatives, with 547 seats, serving as the highest authority of the federal government, and the Council of

Federation, with 155 seats, responsible for interpreting the Constitution (<http://www.nationsencyclopedia.com/ethiopia>.2020/09/23).

In this parliamentary democratic system, executive power lies with the prime minister, who is elected from among the members of the Council of People's Representatives. The prime minister appoints government ministers, members of the Central High Court, and the auditor general, and oversees the execution of laws and decisions, presides over the Council of Ministers, controls the armed forces, and shapes Ethiopia's foreign policy.

Ethiopia's federal system is a response to its long-standing instability, driven by ethnic tensions. Given the country's diverse ethnic makeup and historical conflicts, the adoption of federalism was deemed inevitable. However, challenges persist, particularly concerning the country's dependence on rainfall-dependent agriculture, which remains an ongoing test for Ethiopia's federal structure.

Federal Republic of Germany

Germany stands as a geographical marvel on the European continent, boasting diverse landscapes and a rich historical legacy. Despite its natural beauty and inherent capabilities, Germany has been a subject of political discourse and contention throughout history. The aftermath of World War II saw Germany divided into two parts; a circumstance that likely influenced significant political developments. Following the reunification of Germany in 1990, the country embraced a federal system, while maintaining its parliamentary system of government.

The roots of Germany's federalism can be traced back to its earlier experience with the German Empire. The constitution of the German Empire (1871-1918) is often described as federal in nature, though distinct from the constitution of the United States. The empire comprised twenty-five states and operated on the principle of regional autonomy, with a clear delineation of powers between the central and regional governments (Wheare, 1963, p. 6). Germany's

modern federal system draws from this historical precedent, with the Basic Law serving as the foundation for its federal structure.

In Germany's federal parliamentary representative democratic republic, the Chancellor serves as the head of government within a pluralistic multiparty system. Legislative power is vested in the parliament (Bundestag) and Bundesrat, representing the regional states. Since 1949, the political landscape has been dominated by the Christian Democratic Union and the Social Democratic Party of Germany. The judiciary operates independently of the executive and legislative branches, as prescribed by the Basic Law, which has remained largely unchanged since the reunification of Germany in the 1990s (Gyawali & Raj, 2010, p. 145).

The federal parliament consists of two chambers: the Bundesrat and the Bundestag. Members of the Bundestag are elected for four-year terms through universal suffrage, while the Bundesrat, comprising representatives appointed by the provincial governments, holds absolute veto power over legislation affecting the provinces. Disputes between the two chambers are resolved through a conciliating committee (<http://www.nationsencyclopedia.com/Europe/Germany>. 2020/09/28). The Chancellor and cabinet are accountable to the Bundestag, which directly represents the people, while the Bundesrat represents the Länder, or states.

Germany's journey towards federalism was shaped by its unique historical context, linguistic diversity, and the nature of its connected and fragmented states. Following the Vienna Convention of 1840, which unified forty Union states into the present-day Germany, the country's complex political landscape made a unitary system untenable. Thus, the implementation of federalism became a necessary means to ensure stability and accommodate the diverse interests of its regions. In conclusion, Germany's adoption of federalism reflects its historical evolution and the imperative to reconcile its diverse linguistic, cultural, and political identities. The federal system provides a framework for cooperation

and governance that balances central authority with regional autonomy, ensuring stability and prosperity for the nation.

The Republic of India

India, the world's largest federal democratic republic, is not only the seventh largest country in terms of area but also the most populous. Its cultural and geographical diversity has been a constant factor, shaping its federal nature. Unlike a unitary state, India's language, culture, and geography have always lent themselves to a federal arrangement. The adoption of a federal system was enshrined in the modern Indian Constitution, although some argue that India's federalism is not fully developed, labeling it as semi-federalism. The Constitution of India, enacted in 1950, delineates certain lists of legislative powers, dividing them between the Union and the regional states. While there are fixed legislative powers under both entities, there is also flexibility in certain areas. However, in times of conflict, the supremacy of the central government, or the Presidency, is maintained, reflecting the historical context and the nature of the country.

Structurally, federalism in India operates at three levels: Union-State, Interstate, and intra-state levels. At the Union-State level, there exist two executive sets of relationships: one encompassing the general relationship between the central and state governments, and the other involving special relationships between the Union and specific states to accommodate ethno-cultural perspectives within the framework of Indian federalism. At the Interstate level, there is only one set of relationships between two states. At the intra-state level, multiple sets of federal relationships are observed, including those between the state and regional autonomous bodies, regional councils and Panchayati Rajya Institutions, and the state and Panchayati Institutions (Singh, 2009, p. 9). Constitutionally, India's federal system is divided vertically into three levels: the Union, regional states, and local autonomous units, each vested with certain executive powers. However, India's federalism is considered quasi-federal because the Union holds more governing

power than the regional units, and there exist special relationships between the Union, regional states, and local autonomous units.

The Indian constitution draws from multiple ideological legacies, including the legal transfer of power from the British Parliament to the Constituent Assembly of India and the invocation of the "We the People of India" in the Preamble as the source of political power. The tension between parliamentary sovereignty and popular sovereignty remains a contentious issue, especially since the adoption of federalism in the post-independence era. The implementation of federalism was driven by the imperative of preserving unity amidst diversity, a principle that continues to be upheld in modern India. In conclusion, India's federalism reflects its diverse socio-cultural fabric and the need to accommodate varied interests within a unified framework. While the federal system is a cornerstone of Indian governance, debates surrounding the extent of federal powers persist, highlighting the ongoing evolution of India's federal structure

The Swiss Confederation

Switzerland has been characterized by federalism since its inception in the thirteenth century, making it one of the oldest federal nations predating the modern state. Known officially as the Confederation Helvetica or Confederation of Switzerland, its name holds historical significance, reflecting its foundation as a confederation of independent states in 1291. Initially formed for defense and arbitration purposes, Switzerland's complex treaty system evolved over time. However, with the advent of industrialization and nation-building in neighboring states, conflicts over the organization of the union arose, culminating in a brief civil war in 1847 between conservative Catholics and progressive Protestants (Topperwien, 2009, p. 84). This historical background underscores Switzerland's federalism as a product of its confederal origins.

The Swiss Constitution of 1848, while drawing inspiration from the American constitution, introduced modifications to the strict federal principle. Notably, it established the Council of

States, the upper house of the legislature, composed of two representatives from each canton, with their terms, elections, and remuneration determined by their respective cantons. These modifications, deviating from strict federalism, leaned towards unitarization. (Wheare, 1963, p. 16), reflecting the Swiss commitment to protecting cantonal autonomy while maintaining federal unity.

Switzerland stands out for its linguistic and religious diversity, with German Swiss dominating numerically and economically. Despite three official languages (German, French, and Italian) and two dominant faiths, decentralization is high in practice, with cantons playing a crucial role in administering a significant portion of federal legislation (Watts, 2008, p. 31). The Swiss federation prioritizes democratic principles, empowering regional and local units with the right to self-government within federal and confederal structures. Furthermore, the Swiss constitution symbolizes a commitment to diversity, with the preamble emphasizing unity amidst diversity, and Article 2 promoting cultural diversity (Topperwien, 2009, p. 86). Switzerland's constitution not only recognizes but also safeguards pre-existing diversity, distinguishing it as a country that cherishes its federal character and the unique rights of its cantons.

Switzerland's federal system, rooted in its historical context, remains distinct from other nations. Its enduring adherence to federal principles is evident in its direct election system, a testament to its commitment to democratic governance. The Swiss model serves as a global example of federalism, demonstrating how diverse linguistic, cultural, and religious identities can coexist within a unified framework.

Federalism and Nepal

The Maoist insurgency, arising from discontent with the government during Nepal's second democratic period, became a catalyst for state restructuring. It is widely believed that external forces played a significant role behind the Maoist movement and the subsequent political changes in the country, warranting further research. The absence of public consensus on secularism,

federalism, and monarchy during the drafting of the current constitution in Nepal underscores the contentious nature of these issues. Even today, discussing these matters remains sensitive for some, raising questions about the democratic legitimacy of such decisions. The completion of the democratic process in this regard remains uncertain, given the complexity of these empirical and political issues.

Following the third amendment of the Interim Constitution in 2007, Nepal formally declared itself a 'federal democratic republic.' However, it's worth noting that the initial demand for federalism in Nepal was not a focal point during the Maoist people's war or the People's Movement of 2006. Even the Interim Constitution did not explicitly address the need for a forward-looking federal restructuring of Nepal.

Federalism, as a form of state organization, has gained international popularity over time, suggesting that state builders should consider the advantages of federal solutions. The production of federalism involves various preparatory stages, with historical precedents demonstrating two primary processes: federalism by de-aggregation and federalism by aggregation. While the United States exemplifies federalism by aggregation, Nepal's restructuring process leans towards centrifugal tendencies. The idea of federalism in Nepal emerged as a response to the discriminatory nature of the unitary system, particularly regarding religion and caste. Despite the restoration of democracy after the end of the Rana regime in 1951, significant changes in the power structure were not observed. Ethnic groups began demanding federal restructuring in the post-democracy era, with movements like the Terai Congress advocating for a Terai autonomous state. Various ethnic organizations echoed these sentiments after the 1990 movement.

However, the call for federalism remained dormant until the aftermath of the second People's Movement and the abolition of the monarchy. The Maoists envisioned Nepal's development progressing beyond monarchy, leading to increased demands for federalism in a

republican Nepal. The Madhesi movement further propelled the discourse on federalism, influencing the restructuring process. Although the demand for federalism had been voiced earlier by the Terai Congress and other ethnic organizations, it gained momentum during the Maoist movement and the Madhesi uprising. Despite these developments, the issue of federalism in Nepal has not been without controversy. Critics argue that it may undermine national unity, promote regionalism, and disrupt social order. Additionally, some question whether federalism is the sole solution for improvement, suggesting alternative approaches.

Federalism reflects one of many possible forms of state organization, particularly in countries with multiethnic, multireligious, and multicultural societies. Throughout history, individuals and groups have debated the ideal structure of a state. In Nepal's context, this debate remains relevant, given the absence of significant historical events or movements necessitating state restructuring. The country's geographical, societal, and economic dynamics present challenges to implementing federalism, leading some to advocate for its abolition. Comparing Nepal to other federal countries underscores the lack of inevitability in adopting federalism. While federalism may be suitable for nations with specific historical, social, and political contexts, its applicability in Nepal remains subject to ongoing debate and scrutiny. As Nepal navigates its path towards federalism, thorough research and dialogue are essential to ensure a democratic and inclusive process.

Conclusion

The formation of federalism across various nations reveals a pattern: federal states emerge to either establish or preserve national integrity. Throughout history, the choice between unitary and federal systems has often been determined by significant events such as wars, internal conflicts, or the birth of a new nation. The trajectory of nation-building dictates the type of government system adopted and the structure of the state. Countries like the United States, India,

Switzerland, and Germany have embraced federalism due to their historical federal character. In these cases, federalism emerged as a natural extension of their socio-political landscape. Conversely, nations like Ethiopia and Spain have turned to federalism to safeguard their national unity in the face of internal divisions or ethnic diversity. In Nepal's case, the implementation of federalism occurred without a clear public demand or historical precedent. Unlike other countries with a federal tradition, Nepal lacked significant challenges to its unitary system prior to the adoption of federalism. The centrifugal federal system introduced in Nepal appears to have been imposed without a mandate or referendum, potentially leading to discontent and opposition. The absence of a strong historical basis for federalism in Nepal raises questions about its legitimacy and effectiveness in addressing the country's governance challenges. Without a robust public mandate or a history of federal governance, the adoption of federalism in Nepal may face resistance and skepticism. Moving forward, Nepal must navigate the complexities of federalism while ensuring democratic principles and inclusive decision-making processes. Dialogue and engagement with diverse stakeholders are crucial to address concerns and build consensus on the future trajectory of governance in Nepal. Ultimately, the success of federalism in Nepal will depend on its ability to foster national unity, promote equitable development, and address the aspirations of all Nepali citizens.

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